

Classicization of photon spin and an alternative to special relativity

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Abstract

Today, the true nature of photons still eludes physicists, even just like it did in 1951 when Einstein wrote to his friend Besso complaining about “What are light quanta”. Retracing Newton’s physics thoughts (including calculus and adherence to the light-particle view), this paper shows that a light-speed circular motion is an ideal counterpart of the intrinsic spin of photons. In this way, the photon as a particle also has a frequency and wavelength akin to the wave of media, and the different angles between its spin angular momentum and translational momentum behave as different polarization states; all the energy of a photon purely consists of spinning kinetic energy and translational. Further analyzing the constrained motion of the photon that energizes the electromagnetic energy of electrons, we obtain a classical physical picture of the electron’s spin, self-energy, and magnetic moment anomaly. Moreover, without relying on the so-called time dilation and length contraction—only contemplating a concise differential equation portraying the energy-momentum variation of moving particles—one can more intuitively get the relativistic energy-momentum relation and clarify relevant inferences. The photon (whose product of energy and spin period is the Planck constant) can, therefore, be considered the minimum action quantum and the most elementary energy-momentum carrier. These results indicate that the applicability of the Lorentz transformation grounded in the special-relativity space-time view is merely a mathematical coincidence—the very coincidence caused Einstein’s lifelong puzzlement about “What are light quanta” and gave rise to physics neglecting the medium-like nature of a non-empty, matter-substantiality vacuum.

keywords: photon; spin; electron magnetic moment anomaly; special relativity; energy-momentum relation

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1. Introduction

Now we know the vacuum is not vacant; therefore, it is sure that light quanta (i.e., photons) or electromagnetic waves never propagate in an empty space. The vacuum electromagnetic field (even when overlapping and thus appearing neutral) is naturally a taken-for-granted and incredibly neglected medium required for the propagation of electromagnetic waves. Reintroducing a medium model for the vacuum, one can easily visualize that there is no relative motion between an inertial system and the local static vacuum it dominates (as demonstrated by the Michelson-Morley experiment), and that the light from a moving source will be deflected towards the traveling direction of the source after entering into the vacuum affiliated to a stationary inertial system (as shown in aberration phenomena).

Once the light speed in a vacuum has been determined as the wave speed of static vacuum media transporting energy and thus no longer confines our imagination of the consistency of the mechanisms intrinsic to natural phenomena, we can further identify the spin of photons as a light-speed circular motion. Classicizing spin elucidates the energy form and polarization behavior of a photon and the contribution of photons to the composition of non-photon particles; moreover, it presents a viable scenario for delving into the structure of electrons with a spherical distribution charge[1].

Unquestionably, special relativity has gained a remarkable reputation, and in particular, its energy-momentum relation has been verified by numerous experiments in high-energy physics. However, the postulate of the constant speed of light in a vacuum, one of the two starting points of special relativity, neglects a theoretical possibility that the vacuum electromagnetic field is precisely the medium in which electromagnetic waves transport energy. Furthermore, mathematically, as long as length contraction and time dilation are stipulated, assuming arbitrary x -speed invariance will yield the corresponding x -speed invariant Lorentz transformation (where x -Lorentz factor is $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/x^2}$). Now that the experiments validating special relativity all happened to involve light-speed particles (e.g., photons and like-light-speed neutrinos), could the mathematical relation of special relativity be simply a coincidence of the relative-speed variability of light-speed particles at restricted motion (e.g., moving in non-vacuum media)? Namely, as for special relativity, is there a mathematically equivalent but physically preferable alternative to it?

Given the above, the discussion below is not subject to special relativity and quantum mechanics. Following a physical framework of the universal nature principles that unify at the macroscopic and microscopic levels, we will seek to locate the roots of modern physics applicability and complement them with clear physical pictures, thereby drawing closer to the truth about photons that mainstream theories have disregarded for nearly a century.

2. The classicization of photon spin

Can the spin of elementary particles be classicized? Previously, physicists would frustratedly quip, “Shut up and calculate”;^[2] now, however, it is worth a shot.

Since “empty space” exists not in the universe and electromagnetic waves necessarily propagate in some corresponding medium, the intrinsic distinction between electromagnetic waves and photons ought to be clarified. Mechanical waves such as sound waves, water waves, and seismic waves are vibrations of the medium excited by energy conveying—the electromagnetic wave is not an exception to this nature paradigm—it is also an energy-transfer-induced oscillation of a certain medium. Unlike the energy transported by mechanical waves, which is forcibly constrained by medium molecules, the energy carried by electromagnetic waves is free, discrete, and quantized and thus can appear as photons. In short, the electromagnetic wave is de facto a medium oscillation forced to ship energy, while the photon is, as validated by the photoelectric and Compton effects, conclusively an energy particle that Newton stuck to.

As to why a medium transports energy in the form of waves, the spin intrinsic to photons as energy carriers must be one of the root factors in answering this question. Breaking free from the traditional dogma on light and spin—summarizing the energy-momentum relation, polarization state, and diffractive ability of a photon—a light-speed circular motion, which revolves at a constant angular momentum relative to the energy system of free photons, will effectively be the single option to the classical counterpart of photon spin.

For a free photon with instantaneous spin momentum \mathbf{p}_s (translational \mathbf{p}_γ) and spin radius r_s , its spin angular momentum \mathcal{S}_γ (with respect to the photon energy system translating at speed c ; satisfying König’s theorem) obeys

$$|\mathcal{S}_\gamma| = |\mathbf{r}_s \times \mathbf{p}_s|_{\mathbf{r}_s \perp \mathbf{p}_s} = r_s p_s = r_s m_\gamma c = \hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}, \quad (1)$$

where h and \hbar are the Planck and reduced Planck constant, respectively; $m_\gamma = p_s/c = p_\gamma/c = E_\gamma/c^2$ as a variable denotes the energy-momentum factor of a photon carrying energy E_γ . For simplicity, the letter m with a subscript will be used uniformly in this paper to represent an energy-momentum factor (variable) and mass (invariant).

Traveling at light speed, does a photon (with momentum \mathbf{p}_γ) have the kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}p_\gamma c$? And why is its total energy $p_\gamma c$? Do not mechanically apply the energy-momentum relation to get $E_k = \sqrt{p_\gamma^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4} - m_0 c^2 = p_\gamma c$ and

75 then declare that the kinetic energy $p_\gamma c$ is relativistic. In fact, from a Newtonian perspective, the energy E_γ of a photon
 76 (with wave frequency ν_γ) consists of two parts: spin kinetic energy ($E_k^s = \frac{1}{2}p_s c$) and translational ($E_k^t = \frac{1}{2}p_\gamma c$); it
 77 follows König's theorem and can be expressed as

$$E_\gamma = h\nu_\gamma = E_k^t + E_k^s = \frac{1}{2}p_\gamma c + \frac{1}{2}p_s c = p_\gamma c = m_\gamma c^2. \quad (2)$$

78 Revising the frequency $\nu = m_v c^2/h[3]$ of the De Broglie wave to $\nu = v/\lambda$ (where $\lambda = h/p$ is validated), we can
 79 eliminate the superluminal “phase wave”. Also, this revision will align the energy $E = hv/\lambda = pv = m_v v^2$ (part of
 80 $m_v c^2$) of waving non-photon particles with the photon-wave paradigm: half of $m_v v^2$ results from the translation, and
 81 the other arises from the total directed angular momentum (equivalent to $rm_v v = \hbar$ in this case) of particle systems.

82 Naturally, the so-called wavelength λ_γ of a free photon equals its spin circumference $2\pi r_s$, and its wave period is
 83 the spin period ($T_\gamma = 2\pi r_s/c = 1/\nu_\gamma$), as given in

$$\left. \begin{aligned} h &= E_\gamma T_\gamma = E_\gamma \frac{\lambda_\gamma}{c} = \int_0^{2\pi r_s/c} E_\gamma dt, \\ h &= p_\gamma \lambda_\gamma = p_\gamma (2\pi r_s) = \oint_0^{2\pi r_s} p_s dl, \\ h &= m_\gamma \frac{\lambda_\gamma^2}{T_\gamma} = m_\gamma \frac{2c}{r_s} (\pi r_s^2) = \iint_0^{\pi r_s^2} m_\gamma |\nabla \times \mathbf{c}| dA. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

84 Expressing the Planck constant in the form of the action ($\int_{t_1}^{t_2} [E_k(v) - E_p(x)] dt$) and Stokes' theorem, this set of
 85 equations shows that photon motion follows the least-action principle and that energy is neither originated nor destroyed;
 86 moreover, it suggests that the spin of photons reflects some vorticity field property of a vacuum medium.

87 The intrinsic spin corresponding to circular motion allows some behavior of photons to appear as what is known
 88 as wave-particle duality. The double-slit interference phenomenon can occur in single photons, and it lies mainly in
 89 the fact that the regular wave-like spin of a traveling photon stimulates the regular strain fluctuation of the vacuum
 90 medium. Likewise, the circular spin and the spin angular momentum conservation lead to the polarization of photons.
 91 Let θ ($0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$) be the angle between the spin angular momentum \mathbf{S}_γ of a photon and its translational momentum
 92 \mathbf{p}_γ ; then, one can visualize the correspondence between the spin and polarization:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{linear polarization} &\iff \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}, \mathbf{S}_\gamma \perp \mathbf{p}_\gamma; \\ \text{elliptical polarization} &\iff \theta \neq \frac{\pi}{2}; \\ \text{circular polarization} &\iff \theta = \{0, \pi\}, \mathbf{S}_\gamma \parallel \pm \mathbf{p}_\gamma. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

93 At this point, is the linear polarization of a single photon collapsing from the so-called left-right-handed circular polar-
 94 ization superposition state to a linear polarization classical state—in which its spin angular momentum is perpendicular
 95 to its translational direction, and its traveling track approximates a planar cycloid?

96 Here, we will not pursue the so-called electric field vector of polarization light as it does not picture the particle
 97 nature of photon spin. Draw a coin toss analogy: In a non-weightless environment (where gravity strongly circumscribes
 98 measurements), a coin ends up lying flat on a table (forcing a direction, i.e., confining the outcome), either heads up
 99 (“eigenstate” A, mathematically represented as 1) or tails up (“eigenstate” B, expressed as -1)—we can model gravity
 100 in any direction—but in the corresponding direction, each coin toss will only give us a gravity-reprocessed probable
 101 outcome of 1 or -1 . Then, could the perfect calculation $1 + (-1) = 0$ be used to claim that a coin falling upright is in
 102 a head-tail superposition state rather than a deterministic and single vertical state? Although the confined probability

103 outcome of particle spin can be mathematized to a wave function, quantized physics processes (not just the probability
104 itself) are still uniformly determined by nature laws that exhibit a determinism (or causality) nature at the macroscopic
105 level. Now, Schrödinger’s cat can be given a break.

106 Like Newton’s laws of motion, the time-dependent Schrödinger equation mirrors deterministic nature laws, and it
107 likewise has its application scope—it predicts no electron spin nor does it address electron magnetic moment anomaly.
108 In his *Opticks*, Newton emphasized the oneness of nature: “For Nature being ever conformable to herself,” (*PROP. VI.*
109 *Theor. V*) “Nature is very consonant and conformable to herself,” (*Quest. 31*) and “Nature will be very conformable
110 to herself and very simple.” (*Quest. 31*) Below, referring to the spin and energy paradigms of photons, let’s tackle the
111 spin and structure of an electron with a perfect spherical-shell charge.[1].

112 3. The spin and structure of electrons

113 Molecules comprise atoms; atoms comprise nucleons and electrons; electrons comprise... An electron can annihilate
114 (by pairing up with a positron) and release the photon that carry its energy away, and high-energy photons can also
115 “ionize” ultra-strong electromagnetic fields (e.g., close to atomic nuclei) and thus “transform” into positron-electron
116 pairs. But why do near-light-speed positron-electron collisions create various leptons and hadrons[4] instead of
117 directly annihilating and converting their energy into photons? In fact, this is akin to the process by which high-energy
118 photons energize and “ionize” the ultra-strong electromagnetic field of atomic nuclei, thereby creating positron-
119 electron pairs: Near-light-speed positrons and electrons carry enormously high energy, and they are encircled by an
120 ultra-strong electromagnetic field (which supplies positive-negative charges and serves as a workshop to assemble
121 particle-antiparticle pairs)—where $\mathbf{H} = \frac{1-v^2/c^2}{(1-v^2\sin^2\alpha/c^2)^{3/2}} \frac{(\mu_0 e\mathbf{v}) \times \mathbf{r}}{4\pi\mu_0 r^3}$ ($\alpha \rightarrow \pi/2$; $\mu_0 e\mathbf{v}$ can be defined as a magnetic
122 charge from an electromagnetic symmetry view). Near-light-speed electron-electron collisions have the same result.

123 Adhering to what Newton highlighted, “Nature will be very conformable to herself and very simple”, we can
124 naturally reach a natural deduction: The positive-negative charge vanishing from positron-electron-pair (positronium)
125 annihilation will combine into a positive-negative pair (which should receive the energy approaching the cosmic
126 microwave background and have zero total spin) and be embedded as an element particle in the vacuum medium
127 (which, in terms of electromagnetic properties, behaves as a dielectric with the absolute permittivity ϵ_0); an electron
128 comprises a zero-mass, zero-energy, spheroidal-shell-shaped[1] negative elementary charge and a photon that carries
129 the energy of $E_\gamma = m_e c^2$ and is imprisoned inside the charge. Naturally, governed by energy, momentum, and spin
130 angular momentum conservation, more than two photons could be released when one positron-electron pair (where
131 total spin is \hbar or 0) annihilates and “transitions” back to a ground-state vacuum-charge pair (whose total spin is 0).

132 Now that the mass m_e of an electron corresponds to the energy $m_e c^2$ of the photon inside its spherical-shell charge,
133 we may as well concisely analyze the constrained motion of the photon and its effect on the electron spin. Probably
134 in truth, the fact that different forms of energy can be transformed into each other (Why? And is there an elementary
135 energy carrier in the process?) confirms one of Newton’s speculations in his *Opticks* (*Quest. 30*)—“Bodies receive
136 much of their Activity from the Particles of Light which enter their Composition.”—All forms of energy boil down
137 to the kinetic energy of photons—such as mechanical energy, heat energy, chemical energy, electromagnetic energy,
138 nuclear energy, etc., are all manifestations of the kinetic energy of photons under different constraints. Spinning at
139 light speed and translating (in vacuum) at light speed are intrinsic to what makes a photon a photon; whenever and
140 wherever a photon is in motion, it is always in motion. After being imprisoned inside a negative elementary charge
141 and thus “transforming” into an electron, the photon with energy $m_e c^2$ still moves at light speed inside the charge.

As a whole, the electron, an elementary particle with a simple and stable structure, inherits its spin (spin angular momentum \mathbf{S}_e , speed v , radius r , magnetic moment μ_e) from the circular motion spin pattern of the photon and follows

$$\left. \begin{aligned} |\mathbf{S}_e| &= \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{r} \times m_e \mathbf{v}|_{\mathbf{r} \perp \mathbf{v}} = \frac{m_e}{2\pi r/v} (\pi r^2) = \frac{1}{2} r m_e v = \frac{1}{2} \hbar; \\ \mu_e &\approx -\frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{r} \times e \mathbf{v}|_{\mathbf{r} \perp \mathbf{v}} = \frac{-e}{2\pi r/v} (\pi r^2) = -\frac{1}{2} r e v = -\mu_B. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

At experimental values, the electron magnetic moment $\mu_e \approx -1.001\mu_B$ (where $\mu_B = \frac{e\hbar}{2m_e}$ is Bohr magneton) indicates that the electron spin closely approximates uniform circular motion. The electron spin angular momentum $|\mathbf{S}_e| = \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{r} \times m_e \mathbf{v}|_{\mathbf{r} \perp \mathbf{v}} = \frac{1}{2} \hbar$ has a coefficient $\frac{1}{2}$, definitely created by the vacuum polarization tension of single-charge vortex plane, not showing that the electron spin revolves by 720° in one cycle. For a ground-state hydrogen atom with zero orbital angular momentum, the primary motion of its outer electron is a fixed-center spin (located on an equipotential sphere, no synchrotron radiation), and the relations $a_0 m_e (\alpha c) = \hbar$ and $\frac{1}{2} a_0 e (\alpha c) = \frac{e}{2\pi a_0 / \alpha c} (\pi a_0^2) = \mu_B \approx |\mu_e|$ (where a_0 is Bohr radius; α is fine-structure constant) also imply that the electron spin is an intrinsic circular motion.

The bias of the electron magnetic moment shown in $|\mu_e| \approx 1.001\mu_B$ demonstrates that our calculations ignore certain effects, which need to be considered on a finer level. The mass corresponds to the energy $m_e c^2$ and the charge distribution appears as a perfect spherical shell, from which it can be deduced that the photon inside an electron still remains its light-speed translation and light-speed spin (which is a bound-state spin whose angular momentum generally satisfies $r_c m_e c \ll \hbar$). Naturally, that confined photon can only oscillate back and forth in total reflection at the inner wall of the charge, and its energy vibrates in the static vacuum medium that is inevitably ruled by some massive celestial body (or galaxy), thereby manifesting itself as the electron mass in the form of a standing wave.

While spinning and translating, the back-and-forth oscillation of the bound-state photon will behave as a cycloidal motion, and the electron charge will naturally delay one cycle to do the same. (Note: such a light speed of the charge at quantum levels is an intrinsic property, not contributed by external forces, without relativistic effect.) An arch span $2\pi r_c$ of such a cycloid is the effective electrostatic radius r_x ($r_x = 2\pi r_c$) of a free electron; the charge spinning at light speed with a spin radius r_c will contribute a self-energy correction μ'_e to the electron magnetic moment. Undeniably, Thomson elastic scattering (cross section $\sigma_e = \frac{8}{3}\pi r_e^2$) and Compton inelastic scattering verify that the electron is a particle with a tangible, non-ideal-rigid-body volume. The spherical shell of elementary charges possesses an elasticity that cannot be fragmented but easily penetrated, making it difficult to ascertain the particle radius of an electron.

Leaving aside the so-called electron radius measured under strong constraints (Schrödinger's cat being shoehorned into a smaller box doesn't mean it's so tiny) and looking only at the electromagnetic energy energized by photons, the self-energy of an electron charge ($W_e = \frac{1}{2} \frac{Q^2}{C} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_x}$, $W_m = \frac{1}{2} I\Phi = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e}{2\pi r_x/c} \frac{m_e c (2\pi r_x)}{e} = \frac{1}{2} m_e c^2 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\mu_0 e c)^2}{4\pi\mu_0 r_e}$) will converge to the energy $m_e c^2$ carried by the photon it imprisons. Consequently, we can get

$$\left. \begin{aligned} m_e c^2 &= \overbrace{\frac{1}{2} m_e c^2}^{\gamma \text{ translation}} + \overbrace{\frac{1}{2} m_e c^2}^{\gamma \text{ spin}} = \overbrace{\frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_x}}^{\text{electrostatic}} + \overbrace{\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\mu_0 e c)^2}{4\pi\mu_0 r_x}}^{\text{magnetic}} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 (\alpha\hbar/m_e c)} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_e}; \\ \mu'_e &= -\frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{r}_c \times e \mathbf{c}| = \frac{-e}{2\pi r_c/c} (\pi r_c^2) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{r_e e c}{2\pi} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\alpha\hbar e c}{2\pi m_e c} = -\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \frac{\hbar e}{2m_e} = -\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \mu_B. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

This set of equations, consistent with the classical physics paradigm, undoubtedly unlocks a new physical picture for understanding photons, mass, charges, electron structure, and atomic neverending motion, albeit without introducing new concepts, such as "renormalization"[5] ("a small correction ($\sim (e^2/\hbar c)m_0$) to the mechanical mass m_0 ") as

174 Schwinger did when he accounted for the electron magnetic moment anomaly ($|\mu_e|/\mu_B - 1 \approx |\mu'_e|/\mu_B = \alpha/2\pi$). On
 175 the basis of this framework, we will further examine the motion of bound-state photons inside particle systems.

176 4. An alternative to special relativity

177 In the previous section, we proposed that all forms of energy, at the root, stem from the kinetic energy of photons—and
 178 this is just the origin of the relativistic energy-momentum embodied in moving particle systems. It will be more natural
 179 to derive the relativistic energy-momentum relation from a closer scrutiny of the motion of bound-state photons inside
 180 a moving particle system.

181 The mass m_0 of a particle system, characterizing the energy contained in its system and the inertia it resists
 182 motion-state changes, depends on the total energy of photons ($\sum E_i^\gamma = m_0 c^2$, $\sum p_i^\gamma \vec{e}_i = 0$) it imprisons when it is
 183 relatively stationary in a static gravitational field. These photons drive the charges, which bind them, to oscillate back
 184 and forth in a light-speed translation; the vacuum medium compressed at light speed will burst into a charge-rebound
 185 barrier, resulting in an energy-storable standing wave and a readily accessible neutral equilibrium of the particle-system
 186 spatial position. Meanwhile, these photons spin at light speed and superimpose the total angular momentum of their
 187 free state on the particle system totality, thus endowing the particle system with a steady direction in spatial orientation.

188 When a particle system with mass m_0 travels at velocity v in a static gravitational field, its total energy is $E_v = m_v c^2$,
 189 and the momentum $\mathbf{p}_v = m_v \mathbf{v}$ results from the photons with total momentum $\sum m_i^\gamma \mathbf{c} = m_p \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{p}_v = m_v \mathbf{v}$.
 190 After entering that particle system via the corresponding way (e.g., electromagnetic energy, mechanical energy), the
 191 momentum $m_p \mathbf{c}$ of these photons decreases to $m_p \mathbf{v}$; at the same time, the photons carrying energy $m_0 c^2$ inside the
 192 particle system will achieve a total momentum $m_0 \mathbf{v}$. Due to the energy loss of photons during the inelastic transfer
 193 process, it is clear that $E_v = m_v c^2 \leq m_p c^2 + m_0 c^2$ ($m_p \geq 0$) and $p_v = m_p c = m_v v < m_p v + m_0 v$ ($m_p > 0$).

194 From a calculus standpoint, combined with experiments to analyze the contribution of the increments $d(m_p v)$ and
 195 $d(m_0 v)$ to the momentum differential dp_v —and the same goes for energy (noting that $d(m_0 c^2) = 0$)—we obtain

$$196 \left. \begin{aligned} dp_v &= \frac{m_p v}{p_v} d(m_p v) + \frac{m_0 v}{p_v} d(m_0 v), \\ dE_v &= \frac{m_p c^2}{E_v} d(m_p c^2), \end{aligned} \right\} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} p_v = m_v v = \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} v = \frac{m_0 v}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \\ E_v = m_v c^2 = \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} c^2 = \frac{m_0 c^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

197 where $v = \frac{m_p c}{\sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2}} < c$. There is no length contraction, no time dilation, no absolutization of light speed, and no
 198 physicalization of geometry unacceptable to Lorentz, only the concision and conformability of physics paradigms—we
 arrive at the formula equivalent to the energy-momentum relation $E_v^2 = p_v^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ of special relativity.

199 Conceivably, as the traveling velocity v increases, the back-and-forth oscillating speed (relative to the mass-center
 200 system) of the photons bound inside the particle system will be lower and lower. The energy $E_v = m_v c^2$ of a moving
 201 particle system originates from the kinetic energy of bound photons and consists of three parts: entirety translation at
 202 speed v , bound-state light-speed spin, and bound-state back-and-forth translation, as shown below

$$203 E_v = \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} c^2 = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} v^2}_{\gamma \text{ entirety translation}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} c^2}_{\gamma \text{ bound-state spin}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} (\sqrt{c^2 - v^2})^2}_{\gamma \text{ bound-state oscillating translation}}. \quad (8)$$

204 In this equation, $\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} v^2$ is the classical kinetic energy of Newtonian mechanics; as the spinning kinetic energy,
 $\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2} c^2$ is also classical and can be analogized to the “elastic potential energy” for bound-state photons to regain

free-state light-speed translation. As for $\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{m_p^2 + m_0^2}(\sqrt{c^2 - v^2})^2$, sure enough, it means that the translational speed $\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$ of bound-state photons oscillating back and forth decreases with the increase of particle-system traveling velocity v —we will corroborate it through the Doppler effect of light and the “time dilation” of atomic clocks.

A photon, bound inside a light source moving at velocity v , has a momentum $|\mathbf{p}| = \frac{h\nu_0}{c^2}\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$ relative to the source and a period $\frac{\lambda_0}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}$ corresponding to its standing wave. Let θ ($0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$) be the angle between the source velocity v and the instantaneous momentum \mathbf{p} of that photon when released, which gives the Doppler shift (ν/ν_0)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} p &= \frac{h\nu_0}{c^2}\sqrt{c^2 - v^2} = \frac{h\nu}{c^2}(c - v\cos\theta) \implies \nu = \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}{c - v\cos\theta}\nu_0, \\ c &= \lambda_0\nu_0 = \lambda\nu = \frac{\lambda_0(c - v\cos\theta)}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}\nu \implies \nu = \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}{c - v\cos\theta}\nu_0, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where $c - v\cos\theta$ denotes the “emitted” speed v' of that photon, satisfying $v\cos\theta + v' = c$ (here Galilean transformation).

In the above discussion, we default a local static gravitational field as an ideal inertial frame. Effectively, the inertial system is a simplified mechanical model that needs appropriate modification according to specific situations. For example, the Hafele-Keating experiment[6] revealed that different approximate inertial systems have different “time-dilation” weight. One inertial system, which maintains motionless relative to Earth’s center (weightless in the Earth’s orbit) and does not rotate in the Sun’s gravitational field, approximately possesses an absolute status (where the “world line” is a geodesic, while that of other reference frames is not). Accordingly, when a particle system moves at speed v and height R relative to Earth’s center, its energy $m_v c^2$ can be dissected into

$$m_v c^2 = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}m_v v^2}_{\text{translation}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}m_v c^2}_{\gamma \text{ spin}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}m_v \left(\sqrt{\frac{2GM_\oplus}{R}}\right)^2}_{\gamma \text{ precession-nutation } (E_p)} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}m_v \left(\sqrt{c^2 - v^2 - \frac{2GM_\oplus}{R}}\right)^2}_{\gamma \text{ bound-state oscillating translation}}. \quad (10)$$

The relative speed $\sqrt{c^2 - v^2 - \frac{2GM_\oplus}{R}}$ clarifies the determinant of “time dilation”: entering some stronger bound states, photons (and neutrinos) will travel a specific invariant distance (inside bound boundaries) at a slower speed to regain free states. Thus, the timing-period variation of an atomic clock on GPS satellites versus in labs is given by

$$T_G \approx \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_0^2 - 2R_\oplus g_0}}{\sqrt{c^2 - 3R_G g_G}} T_\oplus, \quad (11)$$

where $v_0 \approx 460 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $\sqrt{R_\oplus g_0} \approx 7900 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, and $\sqrt{R_G g_G} \approx 3880 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$; it is easy to get that the timing speed of the atomic clock on a GPS satellite is faster by about $38 \mu\text{s}$ per day. Undoubtedly, the so-called time dilation claimed by special relativity cannot validate that time could speedily or tardily elapse, and it merely reflects, in essence, that a specific relative translational speed of light-speed particles entering some bound state could be fast or slow.

5. Conclusions

This article presents the classical counterpart of photon spin and a model for photon-carrying energy. Such a paradigm successfully elucidates the electron’s spin, self-energy, and magnetic moment anomaly. Further, we obtain a theory substantiated to replace special relativity. How these results would modify the Standard Model is open to discussion.

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I am grateful that Newton’s thoughts on physics still resonate with me today.

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